

COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE STUDY USING SCILAB, MATLAB, OCTAVE SOFTWARE, AND THE C# PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

Gabriel Henrique Castilho Oliveira, Muniz Almeida Costa, Breno Pereira dos Santos, Enrico Carlos Santos e Santos, Alexander Cardoso dos Santos, Dr. Alexandre Manicoba de Oliveira.

Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia de São Paulo, Campus Cubatão.

{castilho.gabriel, muniz.costa, breno.pereira, enrico.santos, alexander.santos}@aluno.ifsp.edu.br e amanicoba@ifsp.edu.br.

Abstract - In this comparative study, we are investigating how the C# programming language and the software Matlab, Octave, and Scilab, respond to the reading of two specific signals. The first signal is related to the development of microwave absorbers, and the second is about the transmission and the thermal power. We evaluated the performance of each system in execution time and precision, considering each project's specific needs.

Keywords: Modeling benchmark; Software; Numerical analysis; patch antenna; thermal power

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporaneous world, the business and industries utilize technology in different ways to be able to develop and evolve. With that said, programming software is of great importance.

In this article, we are benchmarking the programming language C# and the software Scilab, Matlab, and Octave utilization in two different codes, available at [1]. We are observing and documenting the differences we examined in each of them, and the main points of interest are the answer, the graphic representation, cause even with similar objectives, the software ends up having unique characteristics, both positive and negative

DEVELOPMENT

The differences of the software used for the study, the objectives, and the calculations presented in the codes used to produce this research will be presented below.

Used in various areas of engineering, the “Scilab” software can be characterized as a means of using programming in which the user is free to select codes [2], [3]. This software, which has an advanced programming level, is based on analyzing numbers and making calculations. The software can add programs such as FORTRAN, C, C++, and Java, as well as having inputs capable of structuring data. It will list different tools that are available for the user to use in the system.

Below are two screenshots to show how both the graphics and the Scilab programming work:

Figure 1 - SciLab in operation

Figure 2 - Scilab – 3D example [9].

Known as a high-level numerical computing and programming platform, Matlab is widely used in data analysis and complex calculations. In addition to allowing the use of functions that would take longer to be developed in other programming languages the vast library of toolboxes makes it easier to learn and use the software, allowing the user to express ideas directly and providing the tools they need to develop their project. In addition to Matlab, you can already get pre-installed applications, which helps to develop future projects [3], [4], [5].

The C# is described as an object-oriented programming language derived from the C language[6], where programmers take advantage of its resources and libraries to create safe and robust applications. Over time C# has evolved to support new software development methods with some notable features that include code error detection, a single syntax, and a unified type system [7]. Additionally, C# allows for dynamic object allocation and efficient storage of structures.

The language runs on the .NET Framework, an open-source development platform, more specifically on the Common Language Runtime (CLR), Microsoft's internationally standardized class library that adheres to the Common Language Infrastructure (CLI). Structures in C# are organized into procedures, namespaces, types, members, and assemblies, where types are declared and organized in namespaces, classes, and interfaces are examples of types, and fields, methods, properties, and events are examples of members.

According to [8] GNU Octave is free software and is part of the GNU project under the terms of the GPL license. Developed with syntax focused on mathematical computing with integrated tools such as plotting and visualization, its interface operates using lines of command to aim for the solution of linear and non-linear numerical problems. It was developed by John W. Eaton through a high-level programming language using C++ and STL libraries, initially designed for numerical calculation, solving linear and non-linear problems numerically and going beyond, being used even for group-oriented language, still having incredible compatibility with MATLAB and has numerous similar functions.

It has incredible tools for solving linear algebraic problems, approximate calculation of roots of nonlinear equations, ordinary functions, polynomials, calculation of integrals, and numerical integration of ordinary differential and differential-algebraic equations.

The first code was originally written for MATLAB software in [1] addresses the detection of connection points with poor contact in electrical installations, which can be a significant source of fire risk, the code makes preventive maintenance possible in cases like this. Initially, the problem and the mathematical representation of the conductor with different temperatures are described. The idea is to calculate the thermal potentials along the conductor. Using the iteration method for this purpose, where the potential of a point is the arithmetic mean of neighboring points.

The second code, also originating from [1] is a significant contribution to antenna engineering. Inspired by previous work, this code empowers engineers to explore and optimize microstrip patch antenna geometries. Using various calculations, it allows input of crucial parameters such as frequency and dielectric constant to automatically calculate vital information, making antenna design more efficient and affordable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Both encodings were carried out to calculate thermal power and antenna patches in different software among the most highly rated in the programming areas. We carried out the encodings with C#, Scilab, Matlab, and Octave. Several results were obtained, which are presented in the tables below:

TABLE 1 – Thermal Power

	Octave	C#	Scilab	Matlab
Time	16.1s	14.4s	10.09s	18.9s
Charts	GHAEI	NG	GHPDI	GHP
Iterations	8	8	8	8
Results	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate

Note: GHAEI – Generated with High Accuracy and Easy to Identify; NG – Not Generated; GHPDI – Generated with High Precision and Difficult to Identify; GHP – Generated with High Precision

TABLE 2 – Antenna Patch

	Octave	C#	Scilab	Matlab
Time	7.35s	5.4s	3.7s	8.76s
Charts	GLP	NG	GHA	GHA
Results	GLP	NG	GHA	GAP

Note: GHA – Generated with High Accuracy; NG – Not Generated; GLP – Generated with Low Precision; GAP – Generated with above Average Precision

According to the tables above, it is noticeable that Scilab ended up being the one that performed best compared to the results observed in general, having not only the shortest times and correct results but also graphical representations that are among the best when posted side by side with the other options. However, the differences between the results of this tool for GNU Octave and Matlab could easily have occurred for technical reasons such as the quality of the device where the software was installed, which ended up resulting in a longer debugging time and slightly less accurate graphics. Already standing out negatively, it is crucial to mention the participation of the C# language, which by choosing to use it as a console ended up having the graphical representations of the codes compromised thanks to the limitations embedded in this choice.

CONCLUSION

In a comparative analysis of the performance of GNU Octave, C# (console), Scilab, and Matlab, it was clear that Scilab stood out with shorter execution times and higher precision results, especially in the first code. Matlab also provided accurate results, while Octave prioritized graphical accuracy. However, C# (console) faced challenges in obtaining concrete results and generating graphs.

In short, the specific needs of the project were considered when choosing these tools, assuming the importance of accuracy

against execution time. In this sense, Scilab and Matlab proved to be solid choices, each with their advantages, and although Octave stood out in terms of graphical precision, C# (console) was not ideal for similar tasks.

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